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D5.4 – Final Assessment of the Performance of the Science Platform Prototype

Work Package	WP5, ESFRI Science Analysis Platform
Lead Author (Org)	John D. Swinbank (ASTRON)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Sara Bertocco (INAF), James Collinson (SKAO), Matthias Fülling (CTAO), Yan Grange (ASTRON), Rafael Garrido (IAA-CSIC), Gareth Hughes (CTAO), Klaas Kliffen (ASTRON), Manuel Parra-Royón (IAA-CSIC), Susana Sánchez Expósito (IAA-CSIC), Lourdes Verdes-Montenegro (IAA-CSIC), Marjolein Verkouter (JIVE), Nico Vermaas (ASTRON), Stelios Voutsinas (U. Edinburgh)
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Executive Summary

This document provides an evaluation of the vision for, the delivered capabilities of, and the future prospects for ESAP, the ESFRI Science Analysis Platform.

ESAP is a key part of the interface between the services delivered by the ESCAPE project and the scientific community: it will provide a unified mechanism by which users can discover and interact with the data products, software tools, workflows, and services that are made available through ESCAPE, and it is designed to be extensible and flexible to adapt to the emergent requirements of future projects. The development of ESAP has been the fundamental activity of ESCAPE Work Package 5.

ESAP, in and of itself, does not provide any compute or analysis capabilities. Rather, it acts as a broker between users and the various services which are available to them. For example, ESAP will help users identify datasets which are of interest to them (perhaps by interrogating the ESCAPE “data lake”, or an ESFRI-specific archive), to locate software and workflows which can help them analyze that data, and connect them to services which can execute analyses codes on their behalf (perhaps interactively, such as in a Jupyter notebook, or by scheduling jobs on a batch processing system).

ESAP abstracts the details of the various heterogeneous underlying systems from the user, so that they can use a unified, coherent interface to access all of the various services they need. It does this by adopting a modular, flexible architecture. The user will connect to a service-independent web-based *user interface*, which in turn communicates with the *API Gateway*. By adopting a set of standard programming interfaces and conventions, the Gateway can easily be extended to address whatever current or future capabilities are exposed through the EOSC.

Over the course of the ESCAPE Project, ESAP has grown from a vision to a mature and usable software product, which can be immediately deployed in a range of scenarios. Based on the material presented here, we conclude that ESAP has broadly achieved the goals that were set out at the beginning of the ESCAPE project, and is starting to see uptake in the ESFRI community.

It has also become clear that much of its potential remains to be tapped: major ESFRIs can build upon the systems delivered by ESCAPE to address the extreme requirements of the next generation of data- and compute-intensive infrastructures. We look forward to seeing ESAP continue to grow as an open-source project even as the Horizon 2020 funding draws to a close, and we will continue to seek appropriate funding opportunities to support that effort.

This document is submitted as ESCAPE project deliverable D5.4, *Final Assessment of the Performance of the Science Platform Prototype*.

Contents

1	Introduction	8
2	The ESAP Vision	9
2.1	High-Level Summary	9
2.2	Conceptual Model	10
2.3	Major Functionality	11
2.4	Extensibility and Supported Services	15
3	Delivered Capabilities	17
3.1	User Interface	17
3.2	API Gateway	18
3.3	Authentication and Authorization	18
3.4	Data Orchestration within ESAP	18
3.5	Data Discovery	20
3.6	SAMP	21
3.7	Interactive Data Analysis	21
3.8	Batch Processing	22
3.9	Managed Database	22
4	Requirements Analysis	23
5	ESFRI Case Studies	25
5.1	The Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory	25
5.2	The SKA Observatory	27
6	Future Prospects	30
6.1	Governance and the User Community	30
6.2	Technical Directions	31
7	Accessing ESAP	34
7.1	ESAP as a Service	34
7.2	The ESAP codebase	34
7.3	FAIR software	34
8	Conclusions	35

List of Figures

1	The relationship between major ESAP components	10
2	ESAP in its environment.	12
3	The high-level architecture of ESAP.	12
4	The front page of the ESAP test deployment at ASTRON.	17
5	Asynchronous job management in ESAP.	18
6	Using ESCAPE IAM to authenticate with ESAP.	19
7	The “shopping basket” viewed through the ESAP web interface.	19
8	Query results displayed though ESAP.	20
9	Simultaneously querying multiple archives through ESAP.	21
10	The ESAP IDA workflow.	22
11	Artists impression of the CTA Observatory	25
12	Artists impression of the SKA telescopes	28
13	Data flow from the SKA Observatory to the Regional Centre Network.	28

List of Abbreviations

- API** Application Programming Interface.
- CEVO** Connecting ESFRI Projects to EOSC through VO framework.
- CTAO** Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory.
- DIOS** Data Infrastructure for Open Science.
- DLaaS** Data-Lake-as-a-Service.
- EOSC** European Open Science Cloud.
- ERIC** European Research Infrastructure Consortium.
- ESAP** ESFRI Science Analysis Platform.
- ESCAPE** European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures.
- ESFRI** European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures.
- ESO** European Southern Observatory.
- FAIR** Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.
- GB** Gigabyte.
- GPU** Graphics Processing Unit.
- GUI** Graphical User Interface.
- HPC** High-Performance Computing.
- HTC** High-Throughput Computing.
- HTTP** Hypertext Transfer Protocol.
- IAM** Identity and Access Management.
- IDA** Interactive Data Analysis.
- IVOA** International Virtual Observatory Alliance.
- JIVE** Joint Institute for VLBI ERIC.
- JSON** JavaScript Object Notation.
- KIS** Leibniz-Institute for Solar Physics.
- LHC** Large Hadron Collider.
- LSST** Legacy Survey of Space and Time.
- OIDC** OpenID Connect.
- OSSR** Open-source scientific Software and Service Repository.
- PID** Persistent Identifier.
- REST** Representational State Transfer.

SAMP Simple Application Messaging Protocol.

SKAO SKA Observatory.

SQL Structured Query Language.

STFC Science and Technology Facilities Council.

VLBI Very Long Baseline Interferometry.

VO Virtual Observatory.

WP Work Package.

1 Introduction

This document is ESCAPE project deliverable D5.4: “Final Assessment of the Performance of the Science Platform Prototype” [10].

The ESFRI Science Analysis Platform (ESAP) is the primary deliverable of ESCAPE Work Package 5 (WP5). A fundamentally web-based application, it serves a key part of the interface between the services delivered by ESCAPE and the scientific community, providing mechanisms by which users can discover, access, and analyze the data, workflows, and services which the ESFRIs affiliated with ESCAPE, as well as other research infrastructures and a diverse range of other service providers, publish to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

At the time of writing, the funded ESCAPE project is reaching its conclusion. Substantial development effort has been invested into ESAP and the surrounding ecosystem of software and services. However, we do not believe that the development of ESAP itself is coming to an end: the technologies developed, and the workflows pioneered, have shown real potential for widespread future application. This makes it an opportune moment to step back and assess the current state of and future plans for ESAP. What have we achieved within the context of ESCAPE so far? How can we build upon these achievements in the future? It is that analysis which is undertaken in this document.

At the mid-point of ESCAPE, we undertook a substantial analysis of the performance of the ESAP system as it then stood [18]. This document builds upon that earlier work to describe the sum total of the work achieved across the full duration of the project. Specifically, we will consider:

1. To what extent the prototype meets the requirements which were specified in *D5.2: Detailed Project Plan* [13]?
2. To what extent have ESFRI needs been met by the ESAP development effort?
3. What are the future plans for ESAP development as the ESCAPE project comes to its conclusion?

Broadly, this report is structured in two parts. In the first part, we provide essential context by describing the ESAP system. In §2 we address the overall vision for the ESAP system: what did we set out to build? §3 takes that further by describing what is currently available: if one were to deploy and operate an ESAP system today, what would it consist of?

The second part of this document moves on to assess how successful that vision and implementation have been in addressing user — and in particular ESFRI — needs. In particular, §4 tabulates the documented requirements and compares them to delivered product, while §5 describes how some of the major ESCAPE project ESFRIs are engaging with and building upon the work carried out by WP5.

Finally, we consider potential future enhancements in §6, discuss the availability of ESAP and its integration with EOSC in §7, and provide a summary of the results of this analysis in §8.

2 The ESAP Vision

This section presents a brief overview of the vision for and design of ESAP. It supplements and expands upon earlier discussions [10, 13, 18] to describe current thinking about how ESAP can best meet its goals. The vision is inspired by and aims to address a wide range of ESFRIs use cases that have been expressed by the project partners through the ESCAPE Project Platform.¹ Note that not all of the capabilities described in this section are currently available in the ESAP codebase: see §3 for a description of the current state of the art, and §6 for future development plans.

2.1 High-Level Summary

ESAP may be conveniently described as a *toolkit* for building *science platforms*. By unpacking and explaining those terms, we can best summarize the goals we have been working towards in developing ESAP.

By *science platform*, we mean an interactive web-based environment which supports the full lifecycle of the scientific analysis process: it enables scientists to discover data, access it, perform interactive data analysis and use specialist data visualization tools, run bulk processing workflows, and ultimately publish their results to a persistent archive.

By *toolkit*, we mean that ESAP is not, in itself, intended to be deployed independently. Rather, ESAP provides a collection of software components, design patterns, and best practices that enable ESFRIs or other groups that have a library of bespoke services (for example data archives, or interactive notebook environments) to make them available to a user community in a coherent, consistent, and integrated way.

Using the ESAP toolkit, ESCAPE project partners provide assistance to users in engaging with the services provided in the other ESCAPE work packages by:

- providing a flexible interface for querying and retrieving data from a variety of archives and data repositories, with particular emphasis on those which are stored in or accessible through the services provided by ESCAPE WPs 2 (DIOS: Data Infrastructure for Open Science) and 4 (CEVO: Connecting ESFRI Projects to EOSC through VO framework), as well as the citizen science platforms addressed through WP6;
- enabling users to explore the software repositories, like the WP3 Open-source scientific Software and Service Repository (OSSR), to identify and select analysis tools and workflows which are appropriate to their needs;
- helping users to identify interactive data analysis and batch computing facilities which are accessible to them;
- facilitating the staging of data, software, and workflows to compute facilities, providing access to those facilities for end users, and subsequently retrieving the results of processing.

This relationship between ESAP and the capabilities exposed by the other ESCAPE work packages — and the wider service infrastructure within which it exists — is illustrated in Fig. 1 and explored further in subsequent sections.

By design, ESAP is extensible: rather than attempting to anticipate every possible type of data repository, software, compute system, or other service provider, the platform provides generic interfaces through which it can be extended to encompass new functionality.

¹<https://project.escape2020.de>

Figure 1: The relationship between major ESAP components, described in the text, and a selection of the services provided by various other ESCAPE work packages.

In short, our approach is not to attempt to provide a single, integrated platform to which all researchers must adapt, but rather a set of functionalities from which various communities and research infrastructures can assemble an analysis platform geared to their specific needs. Deploying such a science platform at the scale of a system like EOSC provides a natural opportunity to integrate with the data and computing fabric this environment encompasses while simultaneously accessing the tools, techniques, and expertise other research domains bring to that environment. At the same time, we expect that instances of ESAP may usefully be deployed in other contexts, from providing services to just a few users within a small project, to supporting major pieces of infrastructure; it must therefore be capable of operating effectively at a range of scales.

2.2 Conceptual Model

ESAP, in and of itself, provides no compute or analysis capabilities beyond a simple ability to view tabular data and preview images. Rather, it acts as a broker between users and the various query and analysis services which are available to them. These might include, for example:

- bulk data query systems, which can help the user locate and access data files (images, visibility data, etc) in archives, data lakes, or similar bulk storage systems;
- tabular data query systems, which can help the user find relevant entries in source catalogues and similar relational systems;
- Interactive Data Analysis (IDA) systems, which provide the user compute and visualization tools in a convenient environment with access to relevant datasets (for example, a Jupyter [11] notebook, or containerized analysis application);

- bulk data processing systems, which provide batch (non-interactive) processing of data at-scale in HPC or HTC environments;
- scientific software repositories, which provide access to specialist analysis tools and workflows;

A given instance of ESAP is configured with information about available services². When a user connects, the ESAP instance will:

- help the user select services which are relevant to them (for example, by clearly presenting the available services; by making clear what science cases those services support, by taking account of the user's access privileges, etc);
- facilitate authentication and authorization with the various services, as necessary;
- provide a consistent and convenient way for the user to access services (for example, by providing the user with a single way to enter a particular query, and then automatically translating that to the requirements of each individual service);
- mediate data flow between services (for example, by enabling the user to locate data with an archive query, dispatch the data to the processing facility, and schedule processing of the data on a bulk data processing system).

This relationship is illustrated schematically in Fig. 2: this shows the end user communicating directly with ESAP, which mediates their interactions with a range of other services, deployed across a variety of different infrastructures.

Note that the user communicates with a single ESAP instance, while that instance mediates interactions with a range of different services from a variety of infrastructure providers. The current ESAP system provides no concept of federation between instances; however, this is a topic that we will return to in §6.2.8.

2.3 Major Functionality

2.3.1 User Interface

ESAP is primarily a web application: the central hub (the “API Gateway”) runs on one or more servers, and users interact with it by making HTTP requests. The ESCAPE project delivery includes a customizable front-end application (“ESAP-GUI”) which runs in the browser and communicates with the back-end. This separation of concerns is illustrated in Fig. 3. In principle, it is possible to support alternative GUIs which communicate with the same back-end, although none have yet been implemented. Providing such alternatives is out of scope for the ESCAPE project, but provides scope for future extension of the work if appropriate.

2.3.2 Authentication and Authorization

Users may be asked to log in to access ESAP itself, or to use some or all of the services mediated by a given ESAP instance.

This step is not required: if both the owner of the ESAP instance and the owner of any services being accessed make them available to the general public, then ESAP need not force the user to log in. In general, however,

²This configuration is instance-specific: for example, a central EOSC installation of ESAP might provide access to a wide range of services, spanning the entire EOSC, while an institutional or project-level system may only be configured with information about local resources.

D5.4 – Final Assessment of the Performance of the Science Platform Prototype

Figure 2: ESAP in its environment.

Figure 3: The high-level architecture of ESAP.

users are expected to log in before using the data orchestration services (§2.3.3).

ESAP as delivered by this work package is designed to support authentication through any OpenID Connect (OIDC)-compliant system, although it has only been extensively tested and integrated with the ESCAPE Identity and Access Management (IAM) service.³

2.3.3 Data Orchestration within ESAP

The fundamental ESAP workflow is that the user will query one or more archives to identify data of interest, then dispatch that data to IDA or bulk processing systems for processing, collecting results and forwarding them to additional workflow stages as necessary.

To support this model, ESAP maintains a per-user list of active data items: the “shopping basket”. This basket is persistent: (a representation of) the data the user has selected is serialized as JSON, and the results are stored in a database. Note that the basket is not generally expected to contain a complete representation of the data in question (it will not store multi-GB images or query results), but rather it will contain sufficient metadata that the data can be fetched and manipulated on demand (for example, it will store the query which produces the result in question, or a path or other identifier which enables data to be fetched from the “data lake” or other storage).

Services integrated with the ESAP system are able to edit, augment, and update the contents of the users’ shopping basket.

This shopping basket metaphor extends to include services — such as IDA or batch compute facilities — and workflows from the OSSR and other repositories: as they move through the system, users will be able to identify services or software of interest, and store them for use later.

2.3.4 Data Discovery and Staging

ESAP provides a uniform interface which enables users to dispatch queries to a multiplicity of archive services. These include both federated, multi-facility systems such as the Virtual Observatory (VO) and facility- or ESFRI-specific archives. It also includes the “data lake” being developed as part of the Data Infrastructure for Open Science (DIOS) system in ESCAPE WP2.

The data discovery system adapts itself dynamically to the type of archive being queried. For example, it is possible to query astronomical archives by using astronomy-specific parameters such as the celestial position where appropriate.

When data of interest to the user has been located, if appropriate it is possible to arrange for the data to be “staged” — that is, to be moved from the archive to storage which is available with low-latency from an appropriate analysis system.

2.3.5 SAMP

ESAP provides support for the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA) Simple Application Messaging Protocol (SAMP) [19]. This makes it possible for users of other SAMP-compliant tools — including TOPCAT [20], Aladin [6] and Astropy [2] — as well as archive interfaces like ESASky [12] to exchange data with ESAP. This means that users can take advantage of the advanced querying and data manipulation capabilities provided

³<https://iam-escape.cloud.cnaf.infn.it/login>; <https://indigo-iam.github.io/v/v1.8.0/docs/overview>

by these tools and facilities in conjunction with the possibilities offered by ESAP, maximizing interoperability and avoiding duplication of effort.

2.3.6 Interactive Data Analysis

IDA describes a scientist interacting with a dataset in real time to perform their analyses. That is, they type commands or manipulate controls, and observe the results that are produced or the figures that are displayed. Contrast this with batch processing, discussed in §2.3.7.

The processes and tools required for IDA differ substantially from field to field and from facility to facility. For example, the way that data from the SKA will be analyzed is very different to the processes applied to data from the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). It is therefore essential that ESAP implement a flexible capability for interfacing with a variety of IDA services.

The architecture described in §2.3.1, together with the data orchestration system described in §2.3.3, are designed to make this possible. Specifically, ESAP provides APIs through which IDA systems can access the “shopping basket”, both to retrieve data items and to provide (appropriately authenticated) updates from the IDA system as the user saves their analysis. The expectation is that the IDA system will write substantial data products (such as output images) to bulk storage (such as the DIOS data lake), and return references to them to ESAP for further analysis, but this can be adapted for specific project requirements.

2.3.7 Batch Data Processing

Batch data processing describes a situation which is in many ways similar to IDA (§2.3.6), but with a number of significant differences:

- the work is carried out asynchronously: the user submits a job, and then returns some time later to examine the results;
- the user does not interact with the computing systems while processing takes place;
- processing generally happens at scale, with workflows operating in parallel and often being distributed over multiple computing systems.

ESAP supports this by:

- providing a generic API for interacting with batch compute systems, combined with one or more adaptations of this interface to specific systems;
- providing a user interface for asynchronous processing, where ESAP tracks the progress of user jobs, and notifies the submitter when they are complete.

2.3.8 Service and Software Discovery

ESAP makes use of the eOSSR library developed in WP3 [22] to provide deep integration with the OSSR, and could be adapted to use other software repositories where necessary. This will make it possible for users to discover capabilities which are of relevance to them. In particular, ESAP helps users discover software workflows and compute and storage infrastructure that can be used to execute both IDA and batch processing tasks (as described in §§2.3.6 & 2.3.7).

The user is provided with a range of help in identifying software and services which are of relevance to their needs. That is, based on metadata sourced from the OSSR, ESAP helps the user make informed decisions based on criteria such as (but not limited to):

- software that is capable of processing the types of data stored in their shopping basket (§2.3.3);
- software that is appropriate for the type of analysis they wish to perform (addressing particular science goals, capable of being executed in batch or interactive mode, etc);
- services that are capable of executing the workflow or software package which the user has selected;
- services that are local to the storage location of bulk data, or which can instantiate efficient bulk data movement.

2.3.9 Managed Database

A managed database service provides users with the capability to define and use their own relational databases directly within the ESAP system. It is possible to directly load the results of queries against external archives into the user's database space, and then to submit complex Structured Query Language (SQL) queries to the database system. This provides the user with advanced data analysis capabilities — for example, the ability to perform complex catalogue cross-matching — without requiring that they set up and administer their own database system. Further, it opens the prospect of integrating ESAP with external SQL federation services such as Trino⁴ or openLookeng⁵.

2.3.10 Provenance and PIDs

Processing, controlled and mediated through ESAP, will result in *advanced* data products: refined, augmented, or reduced versions of the input data. These data products, taken together with the workflows that have been used to produce them and resulting scientific publications, form the *research objects* which are the fundamental outputs of the scientific community. In order to facilitate Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) access to data, ESAP provides mechanisms for tracking the provenance of these research objects and will assist users in providing them with Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) [9].

2.4 Extensibility and Supported Services

As described in §§2.2 & 2.3.1 above, the ESAP system is designed to be intrinsically extensible: the core API Gateway provides generic interfaces into which additional services can be integrated with minimal effort.

However easy it is to integrate services with ESAP, it is clearly impossible for the ESCAPE team to integrate *all possible* services: there are simply too many domain-specific tools in use in the scientific community for this to be practical. Instead, the team has focused on:

- providing a number of service integrations which demonstrate key capabilities and facilitate the expressed science goals and use cases of ESCAPE-affiliated ESFRIs;
- providing documentation and examples to make it possible for new services to be quickly and easily integrated with ESAP without direct intervention from the ESCAPE team.

⁴<https://trino.io>

⁵<https://openlookeng.io>

The services which are supported at the completion of the ESCAPE project are described in §3, but further will be added by the future ESAP open source project (described in §6).

D5.4 – Final Assessment of the Performance of the Science Platform Prototype

Figure 4: The front page of the ESAP test deployment at ASTRON.

3 Delivered Capabilities

This section provides an overview of the ESAP capabilities delivered within the scope of the ESCAPE project, and describes how they relate to the vision described in §2. The delivered version of ESAP does not meet the full scope of the vision: this is expected, and reflects the wide scope of the problem domain that ESAP addresses and the potential for future development (discussed in §6). However, these delivered capabilities do provide a flexible and compelling system that ESFRIs and other projects can build upon, as discussed in §5.

Most of the capabilities described here are available through a test deployment of ESAP at ASTRON. This system may be accessed at <https://sdc-dev.astron.nl/esap-gui/>. Note that this system is provided without support to facilitate development and demonstration; the service is not expected to be reliable, nor to be available indefinitely.

3.1 User Interface

The front page of the ESAP test deployment at ASTRON is shown in Fig. 4. It presents an attractive and usable web-based interface that enables the user to rapidly discover which services are configured in this ESAP instance (in the top bar; here, Archives, Multi Query, Interactive Analysis, Batch Analysis, Asynchronous Jobs and IVOA-SAMP). The rest of the interface highlights the available archives: in this case, corresponding to Apertif [16], the ASTRON VO system⁶, the Zooniverse citizen science system⁷, and the general IVOA Virtual Observatory [1].

The interface is a cross-platform web application implemented in React⁸, which communicates with the API Gateway (§3.2) over a REST interface.

⁶<https://vo.astron.nl/>

⁷<https://www.zooniverse.org/>

⁸<https://reactjs.org/>

Run ID	Phase	Creation date	Parameters	Results	Action
batch	ERROR	1 Dec 2022 at 15:58 UTC	2 parameters ↓	0 results ↓	ARCHIVE
batch	ERROR	1 Dec 2022 at 15:58 UTC	2 parameters ↓	0 results ↓	ARCHIVE
batch	ERROR	1 Dec 2022 at 15:57 UTC	2 parameters ↓	0 results ↓	ARCHIVE
batch	ERROR	1 Dec 2022 at 15:57 UTC	2 parameters ↓	0 results ↓	ARCHIVE
runic	COMPLETED	1 Dec 2022 at 15:51 UTC	2 parameters ↓	2 results ↓	ARCHIVE
test	COMPLETED	19 Oct 2022 at 09:07 UTC	2 parameters ↓	2 results ↓	ARCHIVE
Another Test	COMPLETED	27 Sep 2022 at 07:22 UTC	2 parameters ↓	2 results ↓	ARCHIVE
Test	COMPLETED	27 Sep 2022 at 07:05 UTC	2 parameters ↓	2 results ↓	ARCHIVE
batch	ABORTED	21 Sep 2022 at 14:07 UTC	2 parameters ↓	0 results ↓	ARCHIVE
Zoom	COMPLETED	22 Aug 2022 at 14:09 UTC	2 parameters ↓	2 results ↓	ARCHIVE

Figure 5: Asynchronous job management in ESAP.

3.2 API Gateway

As discussed in §2.3.1, the “API Gateway” provides back-end capabilities for the ESAP system. The API Gateway is written in Python, using Django⁹ and its companion REST framework¹⁰.

The API Gateway provides a rich, plugin-based system for adding new service integrations to ESAP. It also provides an asynchronous job control system, shown in Fig. 5, which is used to manage long-running tasks like some queries (§3.5) and batch processing jobs (§3.8).

In principle, it would be possible for alternative or specialist user interfaces to communicate with the API Gateway using the same interface; as of now, however, the authors are not aware of any other ESAP interfaces.

3.3 Authentication and Authorization

ESAP is fully integrated with the ESCAPE project’s IAM service. Fig. 6 shows an example of a user authenticating with the ESAP test system using ESCAPE IAM.

3.4 Data Orchestration within ESAP

Shopping basket capabilities, as described in §2.3.3, are available in the current version of ESAP to users who have authenticated through ESCAPE IAM (§3.3).

Fig. 7 shows an example of the shopping basket visualized through the web interface. Note that the formatting of the contents of the basket varies depending on the source of the data.

D5.4 – Final Assessment of the Performance of the Science Platform Prototype

Figure 6: Using ESCAPE IAM to authenticate with ESAP.

Figure 7: The “shopping basket” viewed through the ESAP web interface.

D5.4 – Final Assessment of the Performance of the Science Platform Prototype

(a) Apertif.

(b) Zooniverse.

Figure 8: Query results displayed through ESAP.

3.5 Data Discovery

Plugins which enable ESAP to interface with a variety of archive systems — including Apertif, ASTRON VO, Zooniverse and the Leibniz-Institute for Solar Physics (KIS) Science Data Centre ¹¹ — are provided as part of the core ESAP distribution. Examples are shown in Fig. 8. Note that the query interface and the form of the results returned adapt appropriately depending on the nature of the archive being queried, so that — for example — the user is given the opportunity to specify celestial coordinates when querying the Apertif archive, but not when querying the Zooniverse system.

The leftmost columns in the result interface give the user the opportunity to select individual rows from the results to add them to their shopping basket (§3.4). In the future (see §6), we hope to extend ESAP to offer more flexibility here; this might include, for example, bulk addition of many rows to the basket without selecting each individually.

Normally, archives are queried individually — that is, the user selects which archive they are interested in and directs the query towards it. However, ESAP also provides a multi-archive query mode in which the user's query is forwarded to multiple archives simultaneously, with ESAP taking care of translating the query into a form which is appropriate to each archive and merging the results to present to the user in a unified form. This is illustrated in Fig. 9.

By default, queries are made synchronously: that is, when the user submits a query it is immediately forwarded to the appropriate archive (or archives) and the user interface is blocked until results are available. While this is appropriate for interactive use, it is not suitable for every archive. In particular, large or heavily loaded archive sites may not process queries immediately or may take a long time to respond. For example, the Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) archive system will group multiple user queries together and periodically execute them at the same time in a “shared scan” [23]. ESAP's asynchronous execution system (§3.2) makes it possible for queries of this type to be handled as background jobs, with the user returning later to collect their results.

⁹<https://www.djangoproject.com/>

¹⁰<https://www.django-rest-framework.org/>

¹¹<https://sdc.leibniz-kis.de/en/>

Figure 9: Simultaneously querying multiple archives through ESAP.

3.6 SAMP

ESAP incorporates support for SAMP using the `sampjs` library¹². Users can transmit data to the ESAP web interface from other SAMP-enabled applications, and from there add it to their shopping basket. Transmission in the other direction — from ESAP to other applications — is not yet available.

3.7 Interactive Data Analysis

ESAP makes it possible for users to execute interactive analysis jobs — in the shape of Jupyter notebooks [11] — through a three-stage process:

1. The user selects from a curated list of available analysis notebooks (Fig. 10a);
2. The user selects from a range of available compute systems which are capable of executing their chosen analysis task;
3. The user is launched into the executable notebook running on the system of their choice (Fig. 10b).

The list of available notebooks is drawn from the ESCAPE OSSR, and it may be augmented by local administrators through ESAP's configuration. The list is searchable and filterable to help the users identify notebooks that are relevant to their needs. Although ESAP as delivered does not support other software repositories, it would be a straightforward adaptation to extend this system to search for software available from sources other than the OSSR.

The available compute systems are defined in the ESAP configuration. It is expected that administrators of specific ESAP instances will customize the listing to their particular needs.

Launching notebooks is handed by the BinderHub¹³. As such, limited computational resources can always be

¹²<https://github.com/astrojs/sampjs>

¹³<https://binderhub.readthedocs.io/>

D5.4 – Final Assessment of the Performance of the Science Platform Prototype

(a) Workflow selection.

(b) Jupyter notebook.

Figure 10: The ESAP IDA workflow.

made available using the freely available MyBinder¹⁴ system, should the ESAP administrator choose to enable it for their particular instance.

Upon choosing an appropriate workflow and analysis service, the user is redirected to the notebook environment. In that environment, a Python library — initially developed specifically to address Zooniverse classification data, but now adapted to a wide range of data types — makes it possible for them to access their ESAP shopping basket, and hence to download or otherwise manipulate the data that they have selected. In addition, the Data-Lake-as-a-Service (DLaaS) system, developed in conjunction with ESCAPE WP2 (DIOS), provides integration between the interactive analysis environment and bulk storage offered through the ESCAPE Data Lake.

Although the current IDA system focuses on Jupyter notebooks, we expect to extend this service to address other forms of interaction in future work; refer to §6.2.1 for further discussion.

3.8 Batch Processing

ESAP builds on the asynchronous job management system described in §3.2 to provide a batch computing environment that is capable of launching jobs to a DIRAC [21] environment, monitoring their progress.

This system currently works with a limited number of pre-defined batch processing workflows. Future work (§6.2.2) may include extension to a more flexible job definition system and integration with additional batch processing middleware.

3.9 Managed Database

A prototype Managed Database service has been developed within the scope of the ESCAPE project and can be deployed alongside the ESAP core. This service currently serves as a technology demonstrator; it is not fully integrated with the ESAP core, and is not yet ready to be deployed in a production environment. However, it points towards potential future development directions (§6.2.7).

¹⁴<https://www.mybinder.org/>

4 Requirements Analysis

ESCAPE deliverable *D5.2: Detailed Project Plan* [13] defines a series of functional requirements on the ESAP system. Not all of these requirements are met within the context of the funded ESCAPE project; some require future development (§6) and/or ongoing work by ESFRIs. Nevertheless, this section summarizes the current progress towards meeting the requirements.

ID	Description	Current Status
R-1	Users should be able to get a list of available data, searchable by different criteria, including keyword, science domain, institute, datatype etc.	This capability is provided by the Data Discovery system described in §3.5.
R-2	Users should be able to get a list of known (VO & other) tools and software for users & publishers.	This capability is partially provided through the OSSR integration described in §3.7. By default, only Jupyter notebooks are exposed to end users as other tools are not supported by the ESAP IDA system; we expect this to be addressed in future work (§6.2.1).
R-3	Users should be able to, for a given project & dataset, query for metadata and aggregate information (i.e. find location of data).	This capability is provided by the Data Discovery system described in §3.5.
R-4	Users should be able to stage a given dataset at the appropriate facility.	This capability is provided by the DLaaS system described in §3.7.
R-5	Users should be able to execute a job on a given dataset, including but not limited to: batch or real-time queries & pipelines, depending on the capabilities of the facility, which need to be made clear to the user.	These capabilities are provided by the IDA system described in §3.7 and Batch Processing system described in §3.8.
R-6	The platform needs to accommodate restricted data access, so that groups of authorised users are the only ones that are able to access a given private data set, shared to them via the platform.	This requirement is handled through access restrictions at the service level.
R-7	Users should be able to select from an existing list of Workflows (Notebooks) and either download, or deploy on available facilities.	This capability is provide by the IDA system as described in §3.7.
R-8	Users should be able to assign PIDs to every digital object that is part of a Research Object.	This capability is not yet available; see §6.2.4.
R-9	User generated data needs to be queryable via ESAP.	ESAP provides access to all data which is available through configured archives, including user-generated data.

D5.4 – Final Assessment of the Performance of the Science Platform Prototype

ID	Description	Current Status
R-10	Users should be able to ingest advance data products generated from data processing and/or data analysis back to the project data archive.	This is an interaction between the analysis service and the archive, which is not currently directly mediated by ESAP. However, using the IDA environment and DLaaS system described in §3.7 the user should be able to arrange whatever ingest is required.
R-11	Users should be able to select computing facilities on the basis of their capacity. E.g. an HPC resource with a specific acceleration (such as a GPU) might be needed because the software to be run requires it.	This capability is not yet available; see §6.2.3.
R-12	Less experienced users (e.g. citizen scientists) should be able to filter the list of available software tools to include only those deemed pertinent to the data that they have selected.	The system described in §3.7 makes it possible for users to search and filter the list of tools available from the OSSR. Future evolution of this work could provide additional assistance to users in locating software that is directly relevant to their data; see §6.2.3.
R-13	Users should be able to schedule computational tasks at regular intervals e.g. to periodically retrieve new classification data from a citizen science experiment.	This capability is not yet available; see §6.2.5.

In summary, of the thirteen requirements described, seven have been met (R-1, R-2, R-3, R-4, R-5, R-7, R-12), three require future development effort (R-8, R-11, R-13), and three are satisfied by the integration of ESAP with other ESCAPE infrastructure (R-6, R-9, R-10).

Figure 11: Artists' impressions of the CTAO Northern Array (upper illustration; credit: Gabriel Pérez Díaz, IAC) and CTA Southern Array (bottom illustration; credit: Gabriel Pérez Díaz, IAC / Marc-André Besel, CTAO).

5 ESFRI Case Studies

The goal of the ESAP development effort has been to deliver a system that is of relevance to the various ESFRIs that are engaged with the ESCAPE project. As such, even more than the requirements discussed in §4, the true measure of success of the project is the extent to which it meets ESFRI needs. In this section, we highlight the ways in which two of the ESFRIs most directly involved in the ESAP development effort have driven the direction of the project and may seek to capitalize on ESAP development in the future.

5.1 The Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory

5.1.1 Project Overview

The Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory (CTAO) [7] will be the world's first ground-based gamma-ray observatory, and the world's largest and most sensitive instrument for gamma-ray astronomy at very high energies. It is currently under construction at two sites — the CTAO Northern Array in La Palma (Spain), and the Southern Array in the Atacama Desert (Chile) — thereby providing access to both the northern and southern skies. CTAO will consist of three classes of telescopes, covering a broad energy range from 20 GeV to 300 TeV the Large-Sized Telescope (LST), the Medium-Sized Telescope (MST) and the Small-Sized Telescope (SST). During the Construction Phase, the plan for CTAO Northern Array includes 4 LSTs and 9 MSTs, whilst the CTAO Southern Array will feature 14 MSTs and 37 SSTs.

CTAO is expected to drive a five- to ten-fold increase in the number of known astronomical gamma-ray sources, potentially detecting as many as 1,000 new previously-unknown objects. It is particularly suited to observing short (less than a minute) timescale phenomena, making it a key instrument in the future multi-wavelength and multi-messenger infrastructure of time domain astronomy.

The primary scientific drivers of CTAO are:

- Understanding the origin and role of relativistic cosmic particles;
- Probing extreme environments;
- Exploring frontiers in physics.

For more details on CTAO and its involvement with ESCAPE, refer to the project’s website.¹⁵

5.1.2 Data Infrastructure

CTAO is committed to providing easy access to CTAO data products for scientists worldwide, together with high-quality scientific software to analyze the data. Multi-messenger and multi-wavelength physics are fundamental to the project goals, so it follows that interoperable data and common access mechanisms across different wavelengths, experiments, and observatories are paramount. CTAO will provide support for open science and FAIR data management principles.

Specifically, CTAO looks to ESAP as the potential basis for a science portal providing access to products and services for its user community.

5.1.3 ESAP Success Stories

Modularity The CTAO team identify ESAP’s modular and extensible nature — described in §2.4 — as important to their needs: it makes it possible to extend the platform to add new services and archives by building on REST interfaces. This helps enable the identified CTAO goals of common access mechanisms. The project has already put this into practice, for example by linking ESAP with the OSSR, as described in §3.7.

Analysis Workflows The CTAO Science Portal will offer data and services to its users and staff, with the aim of enabling user interaction with data products and cross-collaboration and joint analysis of data products. These workflows will build upon new and existing tools, including:

Gammapy [8], an open-source Python package for gamma-ray astrometry that will form the basis of the CTAO science analysis tools; and

AGNpy [15], a software package developed by high-energy astrophysicists to compute of the photon spectra produced by Active Galactic Nuclei.

Both of these packages have been incorporated in the ESCAPE OSSR, and are therefore available for use within the ESAP environment.

Batch Processing CTAO operations will require petabyte-scale data management systems. This will be required for observatory management. Typically, it will consist of automatic batch data processing tasks which may be distributed over multiple data centres.

The CTAO team has been deeply involved in the development of asynchronous (§3.2) and batch processing (§3.8) capabilities within the ESAP development effort. The ESAP batch system has therefore been designed to address the use cases expressed by CTAO.

¹⁵<https://projectescape.eu/science-projects/cherenkov-telescope-array-observatory>

5.1.4 CTAO Science Data Challenge

CTAO anticipates running a *science data challenge* as a way to engage the scientific community with the Observatory's development effort. Their team is currently exploring the potential for ESAP to play a role in such a challenge. In particular, in support of this, they have developed a way of deploying ESAP within a future CTAO data centre using the Kubernetes¹⁶ container orchestration system. Further, they have developed a series of exploratory customizations of the ESAP core, providing:

- The capability to use GitHub¹⁷-based user authentication;
- Additional batch and interactive workflows;
- Advanced workflow search options and improved use of metadata.

Some of these changes have already been fed back to the ESAP core distribution.

As part of this work, the CTAO team identified the lack of persistent analysis environments within ESAP as a significant challenge. This is a potential topic for future development, which is discussed in §6.2.6.

5.1.5 Conclusions

CTAO has been deeply involved in the development of ESAP to date, contributing both analysis workflows and core functionality to the project. They regard ESAP as an excellent toolbox for the construction of science platforms, and have successfully been able to deploy and customize it to their needs. The CTAO team has expressed an interest in continuing to collaborate on ESAP development beyond the funded duration of the ESCAPE project.

5.2 The SKA Observatory

5.2.1 Project Overview

The SKA Observatory (SKAO) [24] is an ongoing effort to build the world's largest radio astronomy observatory. It consists of a pair of radio interferometers, currently under construction in Australia and South Africa. The Australian site will house 131,072 antennas sensitive in the range 30–350 Mhz, while the South African site will consist of 197 dishes covering 0.35–15 GHz; both systems are illustrated in Fig. 12. Test systems are already taking data, and the facility is expected to be operational by the end of this decade.

The SKAO is designed to conduct transformational science, breaking new ground in astronomical observations. The observatory has been designed to address a wide range of key science goals, from testing Einstein's theory of relativity, through understanding the nature of dark energy and cosmic magnetism, to investigating the origins of life itself.

The observatory is being designed to operate for fifty years, so a flexible and extensible system is essential.

For more details on SKAO and its involvement with ESCAPE, refer to the project's website.¹⁸

Figure 12: Artists' impressions of the SKA telescopes: mid-frequency dishes at left, low frequency stations at right (credit: SKAO).

Figure 13: Data flow from the SKA Observatory to the Regional Centre Network.

5.2.2 Data Infrastructure

The SKA Observatory will generate around 700 PB per year of science-ready data products. However, the Observatory itself will not make these products directly available to the scientific community. Rather, they will provide data products to a world-wide distributed network of “Regional Centres”, as shown in Fig. 13. The members of this Regional Centre Network are then collectively responsible for:

- Data logistics, including making data available to end users;
- Data processing, including providing computational and storage resources and appropriate software environments to enable end users to visualize and interact with the data and produce additional data products;
- Data archiving and curation, including data discovery and re-use;
- User support.

The development of this Regional Centre Network is now in its prototyping phase. As part of this, The Regional Centre development effort is now evaluating a number of potential technologies — ESAP among them — for use within the SKA Science Platform [5].

5.2.3 ESAP Success Stories

Precursor Data Archives Data from SKA precursor instruments has been made available through the ESAP interfaces described in §3.5. This informs decisions about SKA archive structure and data delivery mechanisms.

Jupyter Deployment The Jupyter system deployed on the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) cloud has been integrated with the ESAP analysis system described in §3.7. This includes integration with Binder and authentication and authorization systems. Further, the system has been extended to support persistent data storage volumes, and to experiment with the Dask parallel computing system.¹⁹

Data Lake integration Although the design is yet to be finalized, a Rucio-based data management system [3], similar to the ESCAPE Data Lake, is under consideration for use within the Regional Centre network. The SKAO team has had a leading role in the integration of the DLaaS functionality with ESAP with a view to providing access to Regional Centre data services from within the Science Platform environment.

5.2.4 Conclusions

The functionality developed within the ESAP is directly relevant to the SKA Regional Centre Network effort, although some adaptation and scaling will be required to address the massive data volumes and distributed nature of the systems involved. The Regional Centre Network is evaluating ESAP among other technologies for use in their future development effort. We have maintained a close relationship between the projects, and believe that ESAP offers a compelling value proposition. However, it is clear that — whether or not the ESAP codebase is directly used in Regional Centre development — the concepts and techniques pioneered within ESAP will have a seminal role within the SKA ecosystem.

¹⁶<https://kubernetes.io>

¹⁷<https://github.com>

¹⁸<https://projectescape.eu/science-projects/square-kilometre-array>

¹⁹<https://www.dask.org>

6 Future Prospects

In this section, we summarize prospects for future development of ESAP, beyond the funded scope of the ESCAPE Horizon 2020 project. Broadly, we split this topic into two parts. First, we address the question of governance and the user community: outside the strictures of ESCAPE, who will use ESAP? Who will contribute to its development? How will that work be organized? Secondly, we discuss technical aspects of ESAP development: what work remains to fully satisfy the vision expressed in §2? What opportunities are there to go beyond that vision?

6.1 Governance and the User Community

6.1.1 ESFRI and Community Engagement

The engagement of research infrastructures and other facilities with ESAP can take one of two forms.

In the first, major infrastructures — such as SKAO and CTAO, as described in §5 — see ESAP as a toolkit or library of potentially reusable components. For example, the distributed and extraordinarily data-intensive nature of the SKA Regional Centres Network means that ESAP cannot simply be deployed in its current form: that environment is more complex and specialized than even a tool as generic as ESAP can address without modification. However, it is likely that the Regional Centres effort will build on existing libraries and toolkits — like ESAP — to realise its goals (although we note that multiple technologies are under consideration, and the use of ESAP-derived code is not certain). A similar story applies to other major research infrastructures, certainly including CTAO, but also perhaps ESO, JIVE, and other research infrastructures both within ESCAPE and across the wider scientific ecosystem.

A second community of potential users are those research infrastructures which have less exacting needs, and instead are looking for a “plug and play” solution that they can use to rapidly provide functionality to their user community: rather than seeing ESAP as components upon which they might build, they look to ESAP to provide a ready-to-use solution that can be deployed with minimal modification. This use case adheres closely to that expressed in §2. However, it is also resource intensive for ESAP as a project: while users in the first category may be satisfied with usable components and interesting proofs-of-concept upon which they can build, this second category requires robust, production-grade components, with a mature test suite and extensive documentation. They are also more risk averse: while the likes of SKAO and CTAO are able to invest resources in developing ESAP itself, other infrastructures will be reluctant to engage until a polished product is available.

6.1.2 The ESAP Open Source Project

Within the context of the ESCAPE project, ESAP is provided as a mature and well-documented product. However, maintaining that beyond the scope of ESCAPE will take resources and organization. To address this challenge, we propose to continue development in the form of the *ESAP Open Source Project*. Specifically, this will be an effort to maintain and develop the core ESAP functionality as community of users. The project will:

- Maintain the current ESAP code repositories (§7), or arrange for new hosting when necessary;
- Continue development and maintenance of core ESAP functionality on a volunteer basis, following the model of other major open source community projects (e.g. Astropy [2]);

- Work with major third-party efforts, e.g. the SKA Regional Centre Network and CTAO, to incorporate their development into the ESAP core where appropriate;
- Provide a forum for technical decision making including all members of the ESAP user community, including periodic workshops and meetings.

The ESAP Open Source Project will work closely as part of the future ESCAPE Collaboration, and will work with other Collaboration members to ensure that ESAP remains tightly integrated with ESCAPE infrastructure and with EOSC, and to seek appropriate opportunities to fund ongoing work.

6.2 Technical Directions

ESAP as delivered presents numerous opportunities for future development to fully realise, and to go beyond, the vision expressed in §2. It is impossible to enumerate all of them here; indeed, to attempt to do so would be undesirable, as it is necessary and appropriate for the directions of development to continue to evolve as requirements change and new opportunities emerge. Here, however, we suggest a number of goals which follow logically from the work presented in this document, and which describe a compelling case for the future.

6.2.1 More Flexible Interactive Analysis Systems

As described in §3.7, currently interactive analysis in the ESAP environment is based around Jupyter notebooks. While notebooks are currently popular and widespread, other tools are available and may be more appropriate in some circumstances. This can be conveniently achieved by including generic capabilities for executing containerized analysis tools. This would open a wider selection of software from the OSSR for use through ESAP, including making it possible to run graphical “desktop” applications.

Within the context of ESCAPE WP5 substantial effort has been made in exploring this model using the Rosetta platform [17]; a logical next step would be to apply the lessons learned and technologies developed there within ESAP itself.

6.2.2 Advanced Batch Processing

As described in §3.8, ESAP provides support for starting and interacting with specific batch jobs on DIRAC systems. There are numerous improvements that could be made here, including:

- Expansion to operate with systems other than DIRAC;
- A wider range of batch workflows, including interaction with the OSSR;
- Making it possible for the user to define and execute their own workflows from within ESAP.

Further, we note that the DIRAC system itself is under active development and there will soon be opportunities for ESAP to take advantage of its new capabilities including token-based authorization and a REST API.

6.2.3 Advanced Metadata for Job and Infrastructure Selection

As described in §§3.4, 3.5, 3.7 & 3.8, ESAP currently makes it possible for the user to discover data products, to locate software in the OSSR, and to bring the two together on a variety of different computing infrastructures. However, the mechanisms for doing this are relatively inflexible, and rely on substantial user interaction. A

future system could build on richer metadata describing the data, the software, and the computing systems to help the user by suggesting tools or workflows that are relevant to the data they have selected (or vice versa), and by intelligently mapping them to infrastructure based on availability and capability of the computing system and locality of the data.

Some work has already been undertaken in this direction in the context of ESCAPE WP5 and the IVOA, resulting in an IVOA note [14].

6.2.4 Data Publication and Persistent Identifiers

As described in §3.7, ESAP currently makes it possible for users to save the results of their analysis to the ESCAPE Data Lake. However, to fulfil the vision expressed in §2.3.10 and requirement R-8 (§4), a more advanced data publishing system would be appropriate: ESAP should provide a standardized way for scientists to store their workflows and output data products to persistent archival storage, including issuing PIDs to describe their work.

Work towards this system has been undertaken and deployed at JIV-ERIC in the context of ESCAPE, but it has not been integrated with the ESAP core.

6.2.5 Periodic Execution

Requirement R-13 (§4) calls for a system whereby users can schedule tasks to repeat at regular intervals. This might reasonably be extended to include a generic task scheduler interface. Work on this functionality has not been undertaken in the context of ESCAPE, but it would form an interesting extension to current ESAP functionality.

6.2.6 Persistent, Shareable Analysis Environments

The Jupyter environments spawned by ESAP are ephemeral: they exist only for as long as the user's session. In practice, this limits their usefulness: preferable would be for users to have access to a persistent workspace that they can return to repeatedly as they carry out their analysis over days or weeks with their data, software, and other artefacts stored for them. The definition of this workspace, and the artefacts contained within it, could be closely related to the data publication system described above (§6.2.4). An extension would be to make the workspace shareable, so that multiple users can work together on a common project.

CTAO and ESO have both identified this as a key use case, so it should be a high priority for future development.

6.2.7 Production-Grade Managed Database

The Managed Database functionality described in §2.3.9 has been prototyped (§3.9) but is not fully integrated with ESAP and is not ready for production use. Future development should make it a first class part of the ESAP system.

6.2.8 Federation

The vision expressed for ESAP in §2 describes each instance as a fundamentally independent system: no direct communication between individual instances of ESAP is anticipated. An ambitious future vision would be to remove this limitation: to build a network of ESAP systems, each of which can (subject to appropriate authorization) share resources and capabilities with its peers. Users can build on this system to perform

truly multi-disciplinary analyses, while the design of the “network of ESAPs” might begin to resemble the SKA Regional Centre network.

Going further, by building such a network on open standards and documented interfaces (for example, by building on the IVOA Execution Planner described in §6.2.3), participation in such a network would not be limited to ESAP instances; rather, the network could be open to a wide range of different service types and implementations, truly enabling a virtual research environment for open science.

7 Accessing ESAP

7.1 ESAP as a Service

As described in §2, the ESCAPE project itself does not directly provide an instance of ESAP that is targeted at end users. Rather, ESAP is distributed a toolkit that is provided for the use of ESFRIs and other data and service providers who wish to provide a science platform to their user community. We anticipate that these individual ESAP instances will be managed and deployed as part of the EOSC.

7.2 The ESAP codebase

The ESAP codebase is a core part of the ESCAPE project output. As such, before the conclusion of the project, it will be registered with the ESCAPE OSSR and thereby preserved for posterity within the context of the EOSC.

The development code repositories for ESAP, together with documentation and other resources, will continue to be hosted at ASTRON, the Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy, for the foreseeable future. The primary point of entry for this material is <https://git.astron.nl/astron-sdc/escape-wp5/esap-api-gateway/-/wikis/home>.

7.3 FAIR software

ESAP satisfies the fundamental tenets of FAIR software [4]. In particular:

- The source code is published in an open repository and shared under a license compliant with Open Science principles;
- It is registered in the OSSR with enough metadata, including a DOI, to facilitate its discoverability and accessibility;
- Clear documentation is provided to enable installation and use.

8 Conclusions

This document has presented an evaluation of the ESAP — the ESFRI Science Analysis Platform — system delivered by ESCAPE WP5. It has summarized the long-term vision for ESAP development (§2) and taken stock of what was achieved during the funded period of ESCAPE (§3). It has compared these against documented requirements (§4) and the ways in which ESFRI stakeholders are engaging with and building upon ESAP (§5). This analysis demonstrates that the system delivered within ESCAPE meets a wide range of expressed ESFRI needs; it provides an immediately functional product, but also a solid basis for future development by ESFRIs to meet their specific needs. This conclusion is supported by the positive reaction to ESAP expressed by the community when it was presented at the *ESCAPE to the Future* event in October 2022²⁰, at the *ESAP Training Workshop* in November 2022²¹, and at *ESCAPE ESAP and Citizen Science* webinar in December 2022²².

Based on the above, we regard the development of ESAP to have successfully met the goals expressed for the ESCAPE project. However, it also presents an opportunity to go further: the ESAP system provides useful capabilities and has achieved a critical mass which makes it a viable product in the future. Therefore, in §6 we described potential approaches to future work, both in terms of the organization of the project and the technical challenges which could be addressed.

The conclusion of the ESCAPE project marks the release of the first stable version of ESAP, which may be accessed as described in §7. However, we are optimistic that the system will continue to grow and evolve into the future, and we look forward to future funding opportunities which might support that process.

²⁰<https://projectescape.eu/events/escape-future>

²¹<https://indico.in2p3.fr/e/EsapTraining>

²²<https://projectescape.eu/events/escape-esap-and-citizen-science-supporting-science-analysis-and-enhancing-scientific-research>

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